

THE ART OF DANCE AND ITS DEVELOPMENT STAGES

Rasulova Rukhshona

Student of the Uzbek State Academy of choreography

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Annotation. This article analyzes the art of dance and the stages of its development. The dance traditions of each people, the style of performance, the means of plastic imagery, are described as having developed in composition under the influence of historical, social and geographical conditions.

Keywords: choreographic art, aesthetic education, folk dance, stylization, folk dance, stylization, folk direction, means of expression.

Introduction. Dance is an art form. In this (dancer), the harmonic body movement and postures, plastic expressiveness and the creation of an image through facial imitations, rhythm, tempo, composition are the main means of dance. It arose in connection with the labor process of a person and the emotional impressions he received from being. Originally associated with song and word, it has since become an independent art form. Dance has been perfecting and gaining stable forms for centuries. The performer's dress gives clarity to dance images.

The dance traditions of each people, the style of performance, the means of plastic imagery, were developed by finding content influenced by historical, social and geographical conditions. Dance is a component of folk rituals, celebrations. In connection with them appeared khorovod and ritual games. Khorovods gradually got rid of ritual games and began to reflect certain aspects of folk marriage. Folk dance is characterized by themes of hunting, animal husbandry, agriculture, and artistry, as well as the people's struggle against invaders and lyrical mood.

Dance is inextricably linked with music, revealing the content of music through images. Rhythm is important in folk dances, it is embodied in music, the movements of the foot, lake, head and body are subject to a common rhythm, are connected with each other. In expressing the content of Uzbek dances, performers also use a kick, clapping, rust. Some dances are performed with an object such as a handkerchief, a bowl, a cup, sometimes performing folk instruments (scissors, circles, drums, etc. k.) in which he becomes a recluse. In the dance of the peoples of Western Europe, mainly leg movements are important, and hand and body movements depart for it. In the east, hand and body movements are the main tools of plastic expressiveness. The stage dance relies on folk creativity, preserves and develops its heritage and distinctive qualities. It originally appeared in Greece, India and other countries. Composed on the basis of folk dances, professional dances developed at a high level, and various dance systems (in particular, European and Oriental classical dances) were decided.

Greek and Roman dance art made a significant contribution to the development of European professional dance art. In the Middle Ages in Europe, the first manifestations of professional dance appeared only in the works of jugglers, spielmans and skomor oxen. In the

15th and 16th centuries, moreski, ballafigurato plot dances became paintings, and pamphlets and textbooks were created about the dance. In the 17th century, ballet dance performances appeared and dance art was enriched with new techniques. 20-a. and at the beginning "modern" (rhythm plastic) dance appeared. In the 1940s and 1960s, small choreographic works intended for concert performance and pop dance developed in Europe and the USA.

Archeological finds of rock images found in Central Asia, including Uzbekistan, testify to the very ancientness of the dance here. The antiquity, richness of forms and types of Uzbek dance art originates from the fact that our ancestors were mainly connected with agriculture and handicrafts. As early as the time of the Zoroastrian holy book "Avesta", the art of dance was formed and began to develop in two directions - folk and professional dance. During the Greco-Bactrian Kingdom, the level of Turanian dance art made it possible to compete with the dances of Greece, Byzantium, India and China. Thanks to the development of urban culture, this art becomes more meaningful and colorful. By the 7th-8th centuries, dance masters from the cities of Uzbekistan, such as Samarkand, Bukhara, Shahrisabz, and Tashkent, traveled along the Great Silk Road to Romania, Egypt, Western countries, and in the East to China, Korea, and even Japan, and demonstrated their art. For example, the dance of our ancestors "Husyuan'u" was famous in China. Poet Yuan Zhang (776-831) and others. praised.

It appeared in different stages of development on the borders of Uzbekistan during the Muslim era. Dances and games influenced each other and lived side by side. That's why "Beshkarsak" is used in weddings, festivals and events held in cities and villages. games, such as "Katta oyn", "Lazgi", "Kema oyn", "Ashshadaroz" have a great generalization and symbolic symbols. You can find both RPGs and action games. During the Renaissance period of the 9th-12th centuries, there was a real rise in the art of dance. The dances were restored and performed on Nowruz, Mehrjan and Sada holidays. According to Abul Fayz Bayhaki, at that time there were hundreds of artists in the city of Termiz alone, and more than 300 artists came from Termiz to the Amudarya River to welcome Amir Masud. Bukhara, Gurganj, Kesh and other cities also paid attention to dance. During the reign of Abul Abbas Ma'mun (1003-1017), the art of dancing was well developed in Khorezm.

The art of dance flourished especially during the reign of Amir Temur and the Timurids. Women played a big role in it. Diversity, historical layers are clearly visible in Dance. These include games around the fire, games dedicated to the symbols of Anakhita and Rustam, status dances, and Dances such as "Argushtak". "Munojot", "Tanavor", "Lazgi" raqs also took a strong place in the program of qualified performers during this period. Dance masters named Sayyid Badr, Tahir Chakka, Mohchuchuk, Maqsudali, Katta Moh, Kichik Moh gained fame in the second half of the 10th century and the beginning of the 16th century. During this period, the art of dance developed in the direction of folk dance.

When the Bukhara Emirate, Khiva and Kokan khanates came into being, unique styles appeared in the art of dance. During this period, due to growing ignorance and bigotry, teenagers and young men took the lead in the art of dance. And women's dance developed in theatrical programs of compact groups of female artists called sozanda (Bukhara emirate), khalfa (Khiva khanate) and yallachi (Fargana valley) and were shown at indoor parties and parties. Dancers secretly participated in men's gatherings.

In the 20th century, the art of dance is in the direction of Bukhara Dance, Khorezm R., Fergana Dance; as stage folk dance reworked on the basis of modern stage requirements: it

developed in the style of ballet performances using elements of national dance. Each of these directions has passed through several historical stages during the century and acquired its own shape and meaning. A number of national and folk dance teams are known to the world. In this, Hamdamkhan, Yusufjan Keen Shakarjonov, Usta Olim Komilov, Tamarakhonim, Mukarrama Turgunboyeva, Gavhar Rahimova, Roziya Karimova, Kunduz Mirkarimova, Karim Rahimov, Kadir Mominov, Ma'mura Ergasheva, Yulduz Ismashova, Shakir Ahmedov, Gavhar Matyoqubova, Rushana Sultonova, Dilafroz Jabbarova, Kyzlarkhan Dance masters such as Dostmuhamedova and Malika Akhmedova are of great service.

Conclusion. In the period of independence, the art of dance is developing more rapidly. On January 8, 1997, the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the development of national dance and choreography art in Uzbekistan" and the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 101 on February 25 of the same year regarding the implementation of this decree. On this basis, the creative association "Uzbekraqs" named after M. Turgunboyeva was established, and a special fund was established under the association. The Tashkent State National Higher School of Dance and Choreography was established on the basis of the Academy of Choreography. Ensembles of "Uzbekraqs" and "Uzbeknavo" creative associations, creating new dances based on the study and recovery of the folk dance heritage, preserving traditional dances and performing them at a decent level, and training young dancers are giving positive results. The award named after M. Turgunbayeva for national dance performance was established. A number of state and folk dance ensembles (Mas, "Bahor", "Tanavor", etc.), dance masters are in different countries of the world, demonstrating Uzbek dance art.

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